

Large field-of-view two-photon fiberscope offering new insights into neural network activities in freely-behaving mice

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Studying neural networks of a large number of neurons that underlie behaviors in freely-behaving animals is crucial for understanding brain function [1]. In this paper, we report a two-photon (2P) fiberscope of a large field-of-view (FOV) for neuroimaging in freely-behaving mice. The fiberscope is compact (of a 2.8 mm outer diameter) and lightweight (1.33 g), allowing mice with a head-mounted fiberscope to perform complex tasks (Figure 1A-B). Our fiberscope adopted an innovative cascaded magnification scheme involving a scanning compound fiber-optic cantilever [2] and a customized micro-objective (Figure 1C). The compound cantilever functions as a pre-focuser for the imaging beam [3], which allows the use of a micro-objective of lower magnification to relay the focused beam from the cantilever to the sample without compromising the overall magnification (or the imaging resolution). The micro-objective offers a low magnification (~ 1) to effectively relay the cantilever tip scanning range to the sample for achieving a large FOV. The customized micro-objective used 2-mm diameter GRIN lenses and a weak diffractive lens (for managing chromatic aberration [4]). Our 2P fiberscope achieved a $1.2\ \mu\text{m}/15.9\ \mu\text{m}$ lateral/axial resolution (Figure 1D-E), and a large circular FOV of a $550\text{-}\mu\text{m}$ diameter (Figure 1F), enabling sub-cellular resolution imaging of a large number of neurons (~ 500) within a given FOV.

2P fiberscope neuroimaging was conducted in mice when performing T-maze tasks. The large FOV allowed us to identify 19 neurons that were highly responsive to spatial turning behavior among the ~ 500 neurons within the FOV (Figure 1F). We then established a neural network consisting of highly correlated spatial turning neurons (Figure 1G). Here, high correlation neuron pairs are defined as their Pearson correlation coefficient (PCC) is greater than 0.4 [5]. We also analyzed the neural connectivity properties, including (1) the number of highly correlated turning neuron pairs and (2) the average neuron pair PCC versus FOV diameter. The results revealed that a larger FOV led to the identification of more highly correlated turning neuron pairs (Figure 1I). We also find that the average PCC in turning neuron pairs (of a range from 0.17 to 0.23) is consistently higher than the average PCC of all neuron pairs (of a range from 0.01 to 0.02), and reaches a plateau when the FOV diameter increases to about $400\ \mu\text{m}$ (Figure 1J), a size comparable to the lateral dimension of a mouse cortical column [6]. This further suggests the critical need for a large FOV in functional neural network imaging. Our studies demonstrate that our newly developed 2P fiberscope can reliably image a large number of neurons and identify neural networks within a single FOV in freely-behaving mice, which would be otherwise difficult or unreliable to

observe with a 2P probe of a smaller FOV [7, 8]. Our results highlight the significance of using a 2P fiberscope with a large FOV for exploring neural networks that underlie complex behaviors.

Figure 1. (A) Photo of a freely-behaving mouse with a head-mounted 2P fiberscope. (B) Photo of the compact 2P fiberscope of a 2.8 mm diameter. (C) Schematic of the large FOV 2P fiberscope consisting of a compound fiber-optic cantilever and a customized micro-objective. (D-E) Point spread functions (PSFs) of the fiberscope acquired by imaging a 200 nm diameter fluorescent microsphere, yielding a lateral and axial resolution of 1.2 μm and 15.9 μm , respectively. (F) Turning neurons in the FOV (labeled red). The FOV diameter is $\sim 550 \mu\text{m}$, and the image is 10 frame-averaged. (G) Neural network consisted of highly correlated turning neurons pairs (neuron pair are connected by green lines). (H) Calcium dynamics traces of turning neurons in the neural network in (G). Red bars/lines indicate that those neurons fired simultaneously when turning, and blue bars denote that those neurons remained silent when turning. (I) Plot of the number of highly correlated turning neuron pairs versus FOV diameter. (J) Plot of average PCC versus FOV diameter. Red and blue curves represent the average PCC versus the FOV diameter of the turning neuron pairs and all neuron pairs within a given FOV, respectively.

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